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Well-Being Monitoring Within Human-Environment Interactions: A Systematic Review

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57 58 59 **Abstract**

60 The systematic literature review analyzes well-being monitoring through the lens of human-
61 environment interaction to identify the criteria impacting well-being, data sources, and
62 models used to characterize well-being processes. The study addresses two research
63 questions: How are human-environment interactions related to well-being? What is the
64 influence of the spatial dimension on well-being monitoring? Reviewing 73 relevant articles,
65 the authors of the study have found that the dominant approach is anthropocentric,
66 emphasizing ecosystems as services for human well-being, while holistic and ecocentric
67 perspectives are underrepresented. Furthermore, there is a significant lack of quantitative and
68 causal research, especially concerning the feedback loop from human well-being to
69 environmental well-being. Studies are mainly focused on the national or regional level,
70 neglecting the local scale, dynamic models, and the use of modern technologies like satellite
71 imagery. These findings underscore the need to integrate systems thinking and environmental
72 monitoring competencies into sustainability education to better prepare future generations to
73 address complex human-environment challenges.

74 *Keywords:* Human-environment interactions, monitoring, sustainability education, well-
75 being.

76 **Introduction**

77 The profound and multifaceted challenges of the 21st century from climate change to
78 social inequality underscore the critical need to reorient education towards sustainability.
79 This task requires a deeper understanding of the complex, systemic relationships between
80 human societies and the natural environment. To contribute to this discourse, the study
81 presents a systematic literature review on well-being monitoring through the lens of human-
82 environment interaction. The research aims to identify how current academic work
83 conceptualizes this relationship and to reveal gaps that, when addressed, can help shape a
84 more meaningful and actionable approach to sustainability education.

85 The well-being of people in interaction with their environment is receiving increasing
86 global attention. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development aims to improve quality of
87 life, reduce environmental degradation, and ensure long-term sustainability (United Nations,
88 2015; Bundela & Pandey, 2022). The core challenge is to maintain a safe and just operating
89 space (Hjalsted et al., 2021) that respects both environmental and social boundaries. Climate
90 change and related environmental challenges impact nearly every country, and although the
91 EU has made climate action and adaptation priorities, progress remains insufficient to meet
92 the 2030 and 2050 goals (European Commission, n.d.; European Environmental Agency,
93 n.d., Sicard et al., 2021). Human well-being, as defined by the Organisation for Economic
94 Co-operation and Development (OECD), includes aspects such as income, health, education,
95 environmental quality, civic engagement, and subjective life satisfaction (Organization for
96 Economic Cooperation and Development, 2020).

97 However, human activities such as burning fossil fuels, deforestation and intensive
98 agriculture are increasingly influencing the climate and the earth's temperature (European
99 Commission, n.d.). This results in air pollution, drought, biodiversity loss, and rising sea
100 levels, which in turn threaten human well-being (Athanasiou et al., 2020; Davison et al.,
101 2021; Fernandez-Anez, et al., 2021; Hermoso et al., 2022; Igini, 2022; Khomenko et al.,
102 2021; Markonis et al., 2021; Methorst et al., 2021; Nicholls et al., 2021; Senf et al., 2020;
103 Vieira et al., 2023; World Health Organization. Regional Office for Europe, 2021). The
104 Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) emphasizes that human
105 well-being depends on natural resources, which include natural assets (e.g., stocks of natural
106 resources, land cover, and species biodiversity) as well as ecosystems and their services (e.g.,
107 oceans, forests, soil, and the atmosphere). Thus, human well-being refers not only to man-
108 made and financial assets, the skills and future health of individuals, and social norms, but
109 also to the sustainability of natural resources (Organization for Economic Cooperation and
110 Development, 2020). The well-being of people and the natural environment must be
111 considered in their mutual interactions. These interactions are shaped by ethical worldviews –
112 anthropocentric (human-centered), biocentric (life-centered), and ecocentric (ecosystem-
113 centered) – that influence environmental attitudes and actions (Liu et al., 2016; Rülke et al.,
114 2020; Thompson & Barton, 1994).

115 There is a growing interest in understanding local and regional development in terms of its
116 contribution to well-being (Sági & Engelberth, 2018, Tomaney, 2017). It is essential to
117 associate well-being measurements with a local geographical area (e.g., village, community
118 level) in order to be able to analyze the factors affecting the well-being of the people and
119 environment of the given place (Costanza et al., 2016; Fioramonti et al., 2022; Marino &
120 Tebala, 2022; McGregor et al., 2017; Organization for Economic Cooperation and
121 Development, 2020, Veneri & Murtin, 2019).

122 To improve both the well-being of the environment and the well-being of people, it is
123 necessary to monitor how human-environment interaction affects overall well-being. The
124 well-being monitoring process would help manage processes that would increase the positive
125 impact of various factors on well-being and reduce the risk of negative impacts. A well-
126 being-based society should develop tools to monitor all contributors to human and
127 environmental well-being (Fioramonti et al., 2022). Human-environment interaction is a
128 complex system due to the fact both human society and the environment have many elements
129 and processes.

130 To maximize the well-being of both humans and the natural environment, further research
131 is needed to understand how human-nature interactions work and, subsequently, how to

132 improve well-being of humans and environment (Brymer et al., 2019). Several reviews have
133 addressed human well-being from different points of view, such as the impact of physical
134 activities, the importance of educational institutions or the workplace, and the well-being of
135 teachers or children, or residents (Hascher & Waber, 2021; Konu & Rimpelä, 2002; Nielsen
136 et al., 2017; Pollard & Lee, 2003; Raj, 2016). No review has concentrated specifically on
137 human-environment interactions and well-being monitoring.

138 The aim of the study is to conduct a literature review on the concept of human-
139 environment interactions and well-being monitoring to highlight criteria impacting well-
140 being, and the data sources and models used to characterize well-being processes. The focus
141 of well-being research is on the interaction between people and the environment, with the
142 geospatial dimension considered essential. The study analyzes how the following research
143 questions are taken into account in the literature:

144 RQ1: How are human-environment interactions connected to well-being?

145 RQ2: What is the influence of the spatial dimension on well-being monitoring?

146 To answer the research questions, the following tasks have been put forward:

147 (1) to categorize articles according to the type of human-environment interactions, the
148 focus of well-being, and the philosophy of environmental ethics;

149 (2) to determine what type of methods, models, factors, and data sources are indicated to
150 assess several aspects of well-being;

151 (3) to determine the scale of research and spatial dimension usage in well-being evaluation
152 and monitoring.

153 This review also contributes to teacher education for sustainability by offering insight into
154 how environmental complexity and well-being dynamics can be taught. Embedding systems
155 thinking, spatial literacy, and place-based methodologies in teacher education is crucial for
156 preparing educators to address sustainability challenges in contextually relevant and
157 pedagogically effective ways.

158 The insights gained from this systematic review serve as a catalyst for a deeper inquiry,
159 aligning with the principles of action research. This paper moves beyond a mere presentation
160 of findings; it uses these results to reflect on our personal and professional experiences as
161 researchers and to explore how these academic gaps can be addressed to foster greater
162 professional mastery for teachers and more sustainable choices in every individual's actions.
163 By critically examining the limitations of the existing literature, the study seeks to provide a
164 foundation for a more holistic, transdisciplinary, and personally meaningful understanding of
165 sustainability in education. The research aligns with the United Nations Educational,
166 Scientific and Cultural Organization university twinning and networking scheme (UNESCO
167 UNITWIN) Chair's mission by addressing gaps in sustainability education, particularly the
168 need for ecocentric pedagogies and systems thinking in teacher training (United Nations
169 Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2022; Wals & Benavot, 2017).

170

171

Methods

172 The systematic review was conducted in accordance with PRISMA (Preferred Reporting
173 Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines (Page et al., 2021) and
174 recommendations for conducting a systematic review from Khan et al. (2003). The
175 technological roadmap and detailed description of methods are presented in Appendix D. The
176 review process, running from January 2023 to February 2025, involved eight researchers,
177 with one acting as a senior advisor.

178 Between January and November 2023, the research team clarified the research problem
179 and developed two guiding research questions: RQ1: “How are human-environment
180 interactions connected to well-being?”; RQ2: “What is the influence of the spatial dimension
181 on well-being monitoring?”

182 The selection of articles was based on the presence of terms from four distinct groups in
183 their title, abstract, or keywords: (I) well-being, (II) human-environment interaction, (III)
184 spatial dimension, and (IV) monitoring (Figure 1). The careful work of creating search terms
185 was more than just a technical task. It was the first time working together to set the limits of
186 the study, and this process demonstrated how complex and interconnected the topics of well-
187 being and the environment truly were (Figure 1).

188

189 **Figure 1**

190

191 *Search String for Human-Environment Interaction and Well-Being Monitoring Records*

192

193 Keywords (TITLE-ABS-KEY):

194 (well-being OR wellbeing)

195 AND (spatial OR geospatial OR geographic*)

196 AND ("human environment" OR "human-environment" OR "human
197 ecosystem" OR "human nature" OR "human-nature" OR "social
198 ecological" OR "social-ecological" OR "socio-ecological")

199 AND (monitor* OR measur* OR evaluat* OR indicat*)

200

201

202 Inclusion criteria were the following: articles addressing (1) human or environmental well-
203 being, (2) monitoring or evaluation of well-being, and (3) well-being in the context of
204 human-environment interaction. As exclusion criteria, the following filters were used: (1)
205 limitation to article, review or conference paper; (2) language to English; (3) peer-reviewed
206 documents.

207

208 **Figure 2**

209 *Flow Diagram for Systematic Review Including Databases Searches*

210 Note: The number of records is presented according to the search process in March 2024 and
211 January 2025.

212

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214

215 Literature search was conducted in Scopus and Web of Science in December 2023, March
 216 2024, and January 2025 (Figure 2). This resulted in 73 articles selected for an in-depth
 217 analysis (Appendix A: List of Articles Reviewed). The process of double-checking these
 218 results, where each article was reviewed independently by two researchers, was a critical
 219 lesson in academic rigor and a test of the researchers' shared understanding of the research
 220 criteria.

221 The research team drew up the list of questions to collect information from full-text
 222 articles (Appendix B: Detailed Questionnaire). From January to March 2024 and again in

223 February 2025, data were coded using a shared Google Docs file. Each article was reviewed
224 independently by two researchers. This process transformed a vast body of literature into
225 structured, analyzable data, which then became the basis for the insights of the study. From
226 March to June 2024, the results were interpreted and a systematic review report was drawn
227 up. In February 2025, the interpretation of the findings was refined based on the additionally
228 selected records.

229 The methodological approach, while robust and transparent, was also a specific experience
230 of action research. The iterative process of refining the research questions and search string
231 was a firsthand lesson in the fluidity and complexity of defining “well-being” and “human-
232 environment interactions”. Working as a team of eight researchers required continuous
233 articulation of individual understandings of the research context and alignment with a shared
234 framework. This collaborative effort was not just about following guidelines but about
235 fostering a shared, personally meaningful understanding of the subject matter, a process
236 which mirrors the goals of reorienting education towards sustainability.

237

Results

238 The process of conducting the systematic review yielded both the synthesis of existing
239 knowledge and a deeper understanding of the current state of human-environment interaction
240 research. The section presents the key findings, providing a foundation for a broader
241 discussion on how these insights can be applied to reorienting education for sustainability.

242

An Overview of the Selected Publications

244 The review analyzed 73 papers, with 7% being systematic reviews and 93% original
245 studies.

246

Figure 3

248 *Number of Publications per Year*

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250

251 Publications spanned from 2005 to 2025, peaking in 2024 (n=23) and 2023 (n=13) (Figure
 252 3). The rapid increase in the number of studies in recent years is a clear indication that well-
 253 being in the context of human-environment interaction is an increasingly urgent topic on the
 254 global research agenda. Research on environmental and human well-being is a global effort
 255 due to the worldwide importance of environmental sustainability and its impact on human
 256 quality of life (Figure 4). A majority of studies were conducted in Asian countries (34;
 257 35.8%), with a significant portion carried out in China (14; 41.2%), followed by European
 258 countries (28; 29.5%), North America (12; 12.6%), South America and Africa (7 each;
 259 7.4%), and Australia (2; 2.1%). Key contributors included Sweden (5 studies), Italy, and
 260 India (4 each). This geographical distribution suggests that regions facing rapid urbanization
 261 and industrialization are particularly motivated to investigate these complex relationships,
 262 offering a critical resource for sustainability education globally.

263

264 **Figure 4**

265

266 *The Distribution of Studies Across Countries and the Number of Publications per Country*

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268

269 **Figure 5**

270 *Ecosystem Types Covered in the Assessed Studies*

271

272

273 From the socio-ecological system perspective, urban socio-ecological systems were the
274 most studied (n=23), followed by blue, mountain, and forest ecosystems (each n=7) (Figure
275 5). Coastal ecosystems were examined in 6 studies, rural ecosystems in 5, and drylands in 2.
276 Small islands and coral reefs each had 1 study. The “multiple ecosystems” category includes
277 cases where an administrative territory or region is considered a whole, combining various
278 ecosystems. For instance, a study on the relationship between human well-being and
279 ecosystem services in Mainland China examines 2,842 counties, encompassing different
280 ecosystems such as forests, urban areas, wetlands, grasslands, and others (Liu et al., 2022b).
281 The strong focus on urban environments reflects a broader societal concern for well-being in
282 densely populated areas, a key challenge for sustainable development.

283 **Responses to Research Question 1**

284 *RQ1: How are human-environment interactions connected to well-being?*

285 **Human-Environment Interactions**

286 In the reviewed articles, human-environment interaction is described as the dynamic and
287 reciprocal relationship between humans and their surrounding environment. This
288 encompasses how humans engage with, modify, and are influenced by the natural world,
289 including ecosystems, land use and land cover changes, climate, and natural resources.
290 Notably, many articles address multiple types of human-environment interactions within a
291 single study.

292 For their survival and well-being, humans depend on natural resources such as water, air,
293 soil, minerals, energy, and biodiversity. Among the reviewed papers, 52 articles explore
294 human-environment interactions related to the extraction, use, and management of these
295 resources, as well as the ways in which these resources contribute to regulatory or cultural
296 ecosystem services for humans (Figure 6). 21 articles reflect human-environment interactions
297 through land use and land cover changes, 10 articles are related to interactions driven by
298 climate change, and 7 articles analyze human-environment interactions in the context of

299 environmental pollution.

300 **Figure 6**

301 *Types of Human-Environment Interactions and the Corresponding Number of Articles*

302

303

304 While many articles discuss provisioning, regulating, and cultural ecosystem services
305 collectively (Carilla et al., 2024), others focus on specific services (Figure 7a; Appendix C,
306 Table C.1). For example, Liu et al. (2022a) analyzed multiple services (provisioning, cultural,
307 regulating) and their spatial variations.

308 **Cultural Ecosystem Services (CES):** A majority (17; 35%) highlight CES, particularly in
309 urban/suburban forests and green spaces, emphasizing recreation (Capecchi et al., 2021;
310 Chai-Allah et al., 2023; Liepa et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2022b; Samuelsson et al., 2019; Wang
311 & Chen, 2024), a sense of place (Vigl et al., 2021), scenic beauty (Bhatt et al., 2024; Maass et
312 al., 2005; Schwantes et al., 2024; Svoray et al., 2018), cognitive development (Beichler,
313 2015; Santos Vieira et al., 2021; Sharma-Brymer et al., 2024), and foster social cohesion
314 (Duku et al., 2022).

315 **Provisioning Services** are featured in 15 articles (31%), including freshwater (Duku et al.,
316 2022; Liu et al., 2024; Stankiewicz et al., 2023; Yi et al., 2024), energy (Newman et al.,
317 2020), and food (Cai et al., 2024; Duku et al., 2022; Liepa et al., 2023; Schwantes et al.,
318 2024). Additionally, agricultural (Adams et al., 2016; Sitotaw et al., 2024), pastoral goods
319 (Maass et al., 2005), and forest wood (Angelstam et al., 2022; Bhatt et al., 2024; Liu et al.,
320 2022b) are highlighted as key resources for business and biomass production.

321

322 **Figure 7**

323 *Distribution of Ecosystem Services*

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(a) By service type

(b) By ecosystem type

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Regulating Services are examined in 11 articles (25%) (Bhatt et al., 2024; Schwantes et al., 2024; Sitotaw et al., 2024), covering climate regulation (Duku et al., 2022; Liepa et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2024; Yi et al., 2024), flood control (Duku et al., 2022), soil retention (Cai et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2022b; Liu et al., 2024; Yi et al., 2024), and bioregulation (Maass et al., 2005). Urban residents prioritized CES, while rural residents valued provisioning services more than regulating services (Liepa et al., 2023).

Supporting Services are addressed in 5 studies (10%) (Cai et al., 2024; Carilla et al., 2024), with habitat quality being the most recognized (Bhatt et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2024; Yi et al., 2024).

Some articles analyze ecosystem services through specific ecosystems rather than service types (Figure 7b; Table C.1).

Forest Ecosystems: 15 articles (50%) examine forests (Aguilar et al., 2024; Bhatt et al., 2024), urban trees (Thapa et al., 2024; Zhu et al., 2022), and parks (dos Santos Facundes et al., 2024; Li et al., 2025; Zeng et al., 2023), highlighting climate regulation (de Guzman et al., 2022; Klobucar et al., 2021) and cultural benefits (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020a; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020b; Carone et al., 2017; Ferguson et al., 2024; Kajosaari et al., 2024).

Aquatic Ecosystems: Eight studies (27%) focus on marine/coastal systems, emphasizing provisioning services like water (Angermeier et al., 2021; Scown et al., 2017), food (de Alencar et al., 2020), and fisheries or tourism (Bastos et al., 2023; Cordero-Penín et al., 2023; Gašparović et al., 2022; Lähde et al., 2024; Peng, 2020).

Rural Ecosystems and Reef Ecosystems: Agricultural production (Castillo-Eguskizta et al., 2017; Sietz et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2023a; Wang et al., 2023b) and coral reefs (Bartolet et al., 2023; Cobacho et al., 2020) are also studied.

It is noteworthy that not all articles emphasize the positive impact of ecosystems on human well-being. Negative impacts, such as allergies (Rai & Singh, 2020) or invasive species (Mungi et al., 2023) are noted (Vaz et al., 2017; Von Döhren & Haase, 2015).

Studies analyze human-environment interactions through urbanization, deforestation, industrialization, and agriculture, which drive land cover changes and reduce ecosystem services (Figure 8; Table C.2). In some cases, the articles address multiple types of land use modifications simultaneously, such as urbanization combined with industrialization, the provision of green areas, or deforestation.

358

359 **Figure 8**

360 *Drivers of Land Use and Land Cover Change and the Corresponding Number of Articles*

361

362

363 **Urbanization:** 15 articles (48%) address urban challenges (Bastos et al., 2023; Beichler,
364 2015; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020a; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020b; de Guzman et al., 2022;
365 Dennis & James, 2016; Gašparović et al., 2022; Kajosaari et al., 2024; Klobucar et al., 2021;
366 Liu et al., 2022a; Zhu et al., 2022).

367 **Creating green areas:** Five articles (19%) specifically discuss the provision of green
368 areas and the ecosystem services they deliver (Beichler, 2015; de Guzman et al., 2022;
369 Dennis & James, 2016; Kajosaari et al., 2024; Klobucar et al., 2021)

370 **Deforestation:** Three studies (10%) examine impacts on landscapes (Angelstam et al.,
371 2022) and urban climate regulation (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020a; Bonilla-Bedoya et al.,
372 2020b).

373 **Agriculture:** Four articles (13%) analyze vegetation changes over time caused by
374 agriculture in specific regions or land-use changes for farming systems (Herrmann et al.,
375 2014; Kohler et al., 2017; Lamchin et al., 2022; Sietz et al., 2011).

376 **Industrialization:** Three studies (10%) link industrialization to pollution and resource
377 depletion (Bastos et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2022a; Zhu et al., 2022).

378 Land use changes frequently cause air, water, and soil pollution (Figure 9; Table C.3).

379 **Figure 9**

380 *Environmental Pollution and the Corresponding Number of Articles*

381

382

383 **Water pollution** (5 articles, 42%): Industrial activities in coastal areas degrade water
 384 quality (Bastos et al., 2023; O'Rourke et al., 2024), while urban studies monitor pollution
 385 through citizen science (Stankiewicz et al., 2023).

386 **Air pollution** (4 articles, 33%): Research in China (Zhang et al., 2024) and Latin America
 387 (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2021) links urbanization to atmospheric pollutants.

388 **Soil degradation** (3 articles, 25%): Agricultural impacts include ecosystem function loss
 389 in Burkina Faso (Sietz et al., 2011).

390 In China, researchers commonly simultaneously examine air, water, and soil pollution
 391 (Liu et al., 2022a; Zhu et al., 2022).

392

393 **Figure 10**

394 *Types of Climate Change Hazards and the Corresponding Number of Articles*

395

396

397 Human activities driving climate change (Figure 10; Table C.4) include fossil fuel use and
 398 deforestation, leading to: (1) **extreme heat** (4 articles, 33%), i.e., rising temperatures impact
 399 urban and natural systems (de Guzman et al., 2022; Klobucar et al., 2021; Lamchin et al.,
 400 2022; Tilman et al., 2024); (2) **flooding** (2 articles, 17%) that is linked to land-use changes
 401 (Klobucar et al., 2021; Lamchin et al., 2022); (3) **storms** (2 articles, 17%), i.e., increased
 402 intensity affects coastal ecosystems (Sajjad et al., 2019); (4) **ocean changes** (4 articles, 33%),
 403 i.e., warming (Bartelet et al., 2023; Tilman et al., 2024) and sea level rise (Newman et al.,
 404 2020) threaten reefs (Cobacho et al., 2020).

405

406 **Figure 11**

407 *Relations of Human-Environment Interactions Based on the Reviewed Articles*

408 Note: Human components (such as urbanization, industrialization etc.) are highlighted in
409 orange color, and environment components are highlighted in green color.

410

411

412 The analysis reveals a consistent pattern: urbanization and industrialization drive both
413 pollution and climate change, reducing ecosystem services (Figure 11). Key relationships in
414 the causal loop diagram (Haraldsson, 2004) include: (1) Positive links: Urbanization,
415 industrialization, deforestation and agriculture intensify land-use changes; (2) Negative links:
416 Climate change degrades ecosystem services. This framework clarifies feedback loops
417 between human activities (orange nodes) and environmental impacts (green nodes).

418 **Use of the Term “Well-Being” in the Reviewed Articles**

419 The term “human well-being” predominates in the literature, with four studies using
420 alternative phrasings: “health of an urban community” (Carone et al., 2017); “well-being and
421 prosperity of societies” (Cobacho et al., 2020); “well-being of urban residents” (Klobucar
422 et al., 2021); “well-being of the nomads” (Lamchin et al., 2022). Only one study (Stankiewicz
423 et al., 2023) addresses human well-being without explicitly using the term.

424 “Environmental well-being” appears just once in the reviewed articles. Other studies,
425 which are not included in this review (Bakar et al., 2015; Khan et al., 2022; Rigley et al.,
426 2023) employ it to describe environmental sustainability.

427 The reviewed literature prefers alternative terms. Ecosystem-focused terminology is used:
428 “ecological well-being” (Zhu et al., 2022); “ecosystem well-being/health” (Angermeier et al.,
429 2021; de Alencar et al., 2020; Stankiewicz et al., 2023); “stream health” (Angermeier et al.,
430 2021). The reviewed article use quality/sustainability metrics: “environmental health/quality”
431 (Burger et al., 2022; Gašparović et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022a; Sietz et al., 2011; Wang et al.,
432 2023a); “habitat quality” (Wang et al., 2023a); “environmental sustainability” (Angelstam et
433 al., 2022; Castillo-Eguskitza et al., 2017; de Alencar et al., 2020; Gašparović et al., 2022;
434 Klobucar et al., 2021; Newman et al., 2020); “air quality” (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2021; de
435 Guzman et al., 2022; Vigl et al., 2021); “water quality” (Scown et al., 2017; Wang et al.,
436 2023a), “quality of the ecosystem” (Mungi et al., 2023); “habitat quality” (Wang et al.,
437 2023a; Zhu et al., 2022), “sustainable use of natural resources” (Sietz et al., 2011).

438 **Methods and Data Sources for Assessing Well-Being Components and Their**
 439 **Interconnections**

440 Both human well-being and environmental well-being are shaped by the interaction
 441 between humans and nature. Depending on human activities and environmental processes,
 442 these interactions can have either positive or negative effects.

443 To assess the impact of human-environmental interactions (HEIs) on well-being, the study
 444 examined which attributes were measured and how well-being was assessed in academic
 445 publications. Among the 73 reviewed articles, 37 employed empirical measurements,
 446 primarily using statistical methods (Figure 12a; Tables C.5–C.6). A critical finding of the
 447 analysis is the dominant use of statistical methods, particularly regression and correlation
 448 analyses (18 studies each), which identify associations but do not necessarily establish
 449 causation. This highlights a significant gap in the literature regarding dynamic models and a
 450 more comprehensive, holistic understanding of the causal relationships between human
 451 activity and well-being.

452 The most frequently used analysis methods are regression modeling and correlation tests,
 453 each appearing in 18 studies (29%).

454 **Regression modeling** examples include linear regression (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2021;
 455 Capecchi et al., 2021; Dennis & James, 2016; Klobuchar, et al. 2021; Wang et al., 2023a),
 456 time series linear regression (Herrmann et al., 2014), logistic regression (Bonilla-Bedoya et
 457 al., 2020b; Ferguson et al., 2024; Thapa et al., 2024), spatial multiple linear regression
 458 (Scown et al., 2017), subset and threshold regression (Li et al., 2025; Zhu et al., 2022), and
 459 geographically weighted regression (Liu et al., 2022a; Wang et al., 2023a).

460

461 **Figure 12**

462 *Statistical Analysis Methods and Data Sources for Analyzing Well-Being Components and*
 463 *Their Interconnections*

464

465

(a) Statistical analysis methods

(b) Data sources

466 Similarly, **correlation tests**, such as Pearson’s correlation (Beichler, 2015; Bonilla-
 467 Bedoya et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2024; Molari at el., 2024; Mungi et al.,

468 2023; Sietz et al., 2011; Thapa et al., 2024; Zeng et al., 2023), Spearman’s rho (Angermeier
469 et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2024; Scown et al., 2017; Yi et al., 2024), binary correlation with the
470 Phi coefficient (Chai-Allah et al., 2023), and spatial autocorrelation (Sajjad et al., 2019; Liu
471 et al., 2022b; Svoray et al., 2018), are equally prevalent.

472 Group comparison and multivariate analysis techniques are also commonly used, each
473 appearing in 13 studies (21%). **Group comparison** methods include t-tests (Herrmann et al.,
474 2014), ANOVA for comparing multiple groups (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2021; Capecchi et al.,
475 2021; Castillo-Eguskitza et al., 2017; Dennis & James, 2016; Duku et al., 2022; Klobuchar, et
476 al. 2021; Molari at el., 2024), the Kruskal-Wallis test for non-parametric data (Beichler,
477 2015; Santos Vieira et al., 2021; Thapa et al., 2024), and Dagum Gini coefficient calculations
478 (Zhang et al., 2024). The Wilcoxon test is also used to compare social-ecological indicators
479 across clusters (Liu et al., 2022b).

480 **Multivariate analysis** techniques, such as clustering or classification (Bonilla-Bedoya et
481 al., 2020b; dos Santos Facundes et al., 2024; Santos Vieira et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2023b;
482 Liu et al., 2022b; Zhang et al., 2024; Zeng et al., 2023), principal component analysis
483 (Castillo-Eguskitza et al., 2017; Sietz et al., 2011), and factor analysis (Bonilla-Bedoya et al.,
484 2020a; Duku et al., 2022; Ferguson et al., 2024; Santos Vieira et al., 2021) are similarly
485 prominent.

486 Other methods include Super-SBM models (Zhu et al., 2022), InVEST models (Bastos et
487 al., 2023; Cai et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023a; Yi et al., 2024), and text
488 mining using the Word2vec technique (Chai-Allah et al., 2023; Li et al., 2025). Spatial
489 clustering was analyzed using Getis-Ord G_i^* statistics (Liepa et al., 2023), while social media
490 data and AI were used to assess cultural ecosystem services. For example, Santos Vieira et al.
491 (2021) analyzed 21,789 Flickr photos along the Brazilian coastline, and Vigl et al. (2021)
492 studied 640,000 photo tags from the Dolomites to map public appreciation for aesthetic,
493 recreational, and cultural values, offering tools for sustainable environmental management
494 and landscape planning.

495 The research team has observed that 27 studies (46%) rely on publicly available databases
496 to quantitatively assess well-being and explore relationships between its components
497 (Figure 12b; Table C.7). Examples of such data sources include standardized well-being
498 indicators – the Human Well-being Index (Angermeier et al., 2021; Scown et al., 2017),
499 national statistical yearbooks (Zhu et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2024); user-generated data –
500 geotagged photos from Flickr (Santos Vieira et al., 2021; Svoray et al., 2018); the public
501 eBird database (Chen et al., 2023), the Wikiloc portal with outdoor trails data (Chai-Allah, et
502 al., 2023); environmental monitoring systems – the European Nature Information System
503 (Castillo-Eguskitza et al., 2017), the Malmö geodatabase (Klobuchar, et al., 2021), and other
504 similar databases.

505 Remote sensing methods are employed in 17% of studies (10 papers): images from
506 Landsat sensors (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020a; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020b; Bonilla-Bedoya
507 et al., 2021; Li et al., 2025), or Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) data
508 (Herrmann et al., 2014; Sajjad et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2023a) are used.

509 Some studies collect their own data, obtained through surveys or interviews (14; 24%),
510 sampling and inventory (3; 5%), or participatory methods (4; 7%). It should be noted that
511 there are studies where the data have been obtained by performing electroencephalography
512 measurements on research participants or by placing participants in a virtual reality
513 environment (1; 2%).

514 **Measurements of HEI Impact on Human and Environmental Well-Being**

515 **HEI Impact on Environmental Well-Being**

516 Environmental well-being, influenced by land-use changes, climate change, or ecosystem
517 service consumption, is assessed in 16 publications (Table C.8). These articles focus on the
518 quality of ecosystem services (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020b; Cai et al., 2024; Junker et al.,
519 2015; Kajosaari et al., 2024; Klobuchar, et al. 2021; Liu et al., 2024; Santos Vieira et al.,
520 2021; Scown et al., 2017; Sietz et al., 2011; Yi et al., 2024), habitat quality (Bastos et al.,
521 2023; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2021; Mungi et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2023a), biodiversity
522 (Dennis & James, 2016), as well as environmental degradation due to natural hazards (Sajjad
523 et al., 2019).

524 **HEI Impact on Quality and Provision of Ecosystem Services (11 publications)**

525 Human activities significantly influence ecosystem services through land-use changes and
526 resource consumption. Watershed quality depends on hydrological functions, using spatial
527 multiple linear regression, a total of 77% of the variance in the mean county watershed
528 quality index can be explained by belonging to ecoregion, industry dependence, and
529 governance by state (Scown et al., 2017). Sietz et al. (2011) quantified the most important
530 dimensions including poverty, water scarcity, soil degradation, natural agro-constraints, and
531 isolation. However, not all dimensions were correlated, the highest correlation coefficients
532 were between isolation (road density) and the severity of human-induced soil degradation (-
533 0.33) and natural agro-constraints (agro-potential) (0.55). Another direction is the provision
534 of ecosystem services in an urban environment, such as planting trees and shrubs in private
535 areas, which can also enhance the well-being of urban residents. Klobuchar et al. (2021)
536 found that potential plantable space of private houses and house age positively correlated
537 with planted area, but years of residence negatively correlated with the likelihood of tree
538 planting. In their study, Dennis and James (2016) indicate that the biodiversity in urban green
539 areas is influenced by volunteers; according to the linear regression analysis, site volunteer
540 input accounted for 93% of the variation in site biodiversity potential. Bonilla-Bedoya et al.
541 (2020a) indicate factors that influence the conversion of forests and green areas into urban
542 environments. For example, according to the spatial binomial logistic regression model, the
543 following predictors increase the probability of urban processes – built-up land, consumption
544 of drinking water, and sewerage indicators. Kajosaari et al. (2024) investigated the
545 characteristics of urban green areas that contributed to their perceived quality among local
546 populations, concluding that the relationship between area characteristics and perceived
547 quality was rarely linear. While the presence of blue elements and higher forest biodiversity
548 significantly improved perceptions of urban green area quality, their absence did not
549 necessarily lead to negative perceptions. Junker et al. (2015) analyzed the data using
550 generalized linear models and found that different measures of socio-economic conditions
551 could have opposing effects on wildlife population. On the one hand, chimpanzee density
552 was spatially linked to a lack of education and a limited supply of fish protein. On the other
553 hand, areas with better economic and infrastructure development reduced large mammal
554 species richness compared to less developed areas.

555 Cultural ecosystem services (CES) are also important contributors to human well-being,
556 for example, through spiritual enrichment, cognitive development, recreation, and aesthetic
557 experiences. Santos Vieira et al. (2021), using the Kruskal-Wallis test, concluded that the
558 counts and richness of CES were higher in areas with higher protection compared to
559 unprotected areas.

560 **HEI Impact on Habitat Quality (4 publications)**

561 Pollution and land cover changes directly impact habitats. Bastos et al. (2023) conclude

562 that coastal habitats face pollution from industrial activities. Bonilla-Bedoya et al. (2021)
563 used linear regression models to explain (with $r^2 > 0.6$) the spatiotemporal variation in the
564 amounts of air pollutants (CO, PM_{2.5}, and O₃). They concluded that both land cover and an
565 increase in forest and impervious cover significantly explain (< 0.001) the variation in the
566 amounts of these three pollutants. Mungi et al. (2023) used the maximum entropy (MaxEnt)
567 method to assess habitat suitability for selected invasive plants in India and noted that the
568 drivers differed for each species. Wang et al. (2023) concluded that habitat quality was
569 positively influenced by fractional vegetation cover and soil moisture content, but negatively
570 influenced by the proportion of cultivated land and proportion of built-up land.

571 **HEI Impact on Ecosystem Resilience (1 publication)**

572 Climate change initiates natural hazards that also affect human well-being. Sajjad et al.
573 (2019) assessed ecosystem resilience to typhoon-induced destruction. Ecological dimension
574 indicators (e.g., parks and forests) contribute positively to resilience, whereas urban areas
575 contribute negatively; tourist flows can contribute to the economic growth of communities
576 that can lead to widened opportunities to invest more in public safety through local fiscal
577 expenditure. A negative relationship between native population size and resilience was found
578 – areas with larger native populations provided fewer opportunities for the non-native
579 population to migrate into these areas.

580 Figure 13 presents the analysis of the reviewed articles on the impact of human-
581 environmental interactions on environmental well-being, their relationship to human well-
582 being, and related factors. The black lines represent causations, they are not quantitatively
583 related, but their theoretical existence is indicated in the examined studies. Moreover, the plus
584 sign (+) denotes an increasing effect, and the minus sign (-) denotes a reducing effect. Green
585 lines represent quantitative indicators that appear in the reviewed studies, but whose
586 causation is not precisely determined by the studies, so mutual effects with arrows is not
587 indicated. Thus, Figure 13 shows that environmental well-being characterized by
588 biodiversity, habitat quality and resilience is related to socio-economic factors, such as
589 dependence on industry, agro-constraints, road density, invested volunteer work, etc., and
590 environmental factors such as ecoregion, watersheds quality, water availability, soil
591 degradation, and availability of green areas.

592

593 **Figure 13**

594 *Environmental Well-Being and Relations with Environmental and Socio-Economic Factors*

595 Note: The green lines represent relations between quantitative indicators. The black lines
596 represent theoretical causations. Human components are highlighted in orange, and
597 environment components are highlighted in green.

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600

601 **HEI Impact on Human Well-Being**

602 Human well-being measurements have been conducted in 22 publications (Table C.9),
603 with a focus on how ecosystem service consumption and land use and land cover changes
604 impact well-being.

605 **HEI Impact on Subjective Well-Being (satisfaction with CES and living in restoring
606 areas)**

607 In the reviewed articles, subjective well-being is characterized by happiness (Wang et al.,
608 2023b) or, more specifically, by a person's happy facial expressions in photographs (Svoray
609 et al., 2018), as well as by satisfaction with the CES supply (Beichler, 2015; Ferguson et al.,
610 2024; Li et al., 2025; Molari et al., 2024; Zeng et al., 2023). The review of the selected
611 articles has revealed that there have been studies that refer to the city of Ecuador, in which
612 no relationship between urban green areas or forests and subjective well-being has been
613 discovered (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020a).

614 **HEI Impact on Health (forests, mountains, urban green areas and biodiversity)**

615 The second dimension of human well-being is attributed to human health and quality of
616 life. In the studies of the reviewed articles, human health is characterized by such measurable
617 attributes as stress level (Capecchi et al., 2021) and perceived restoration (Bonilla-Bedoya et
618 al., 2020a; Chai-Allah et al., 2023), life expectancy, age-specific mortality risk, cause-
619 specific mortality rate (Chen et al., 2023), and obesity prevalence (Angermeier et al., 2021).
620 Some of these studies conclude that forests and mountainous areas have beneficial effects on
621 human health. For example, Capecchi et al. (2021) calculated the potential of different types
622 of forests for stress recovery and concluded that although all types of forests caused less
623 stress compared to the urban environment, the type of forest was important. The deciduous
624 category has a lower suitability value than conifers, in particular in winter time. Additionally,
625 coppices are perceived less favorably than high forests. The third aspect studied is the
626 hilliness of the territory. The authors concluded that the suitability of forests for stress

627 reduction value was indirectly proportional to altitude in both winter and summer. Chen et al.
628 (2023) claim that human health is related to the biodiversity of the surrounding area, for
629 example, the biodiversity of rare species of birds. Their study uses Pearson's correlation test
630 and although the correlations are statistically significant they are very weak. For example, the
631 correlation between regional rarefied species richness of birds and life expectancy at the
632 county level is $r = 0.18$ ($p < 0.001$), while the correlation with the percentage increase in life
633 expectancy is $r = 0.17$ ($p < 0.001$). Rarefied species richness of birds was negatively
634 correlated with the majority of cause-specific deaths, for example, for cardiovascular diseases
635 $r = -0.242$.

636 **HEI Impact on Human Livelihoods by Living in Protected Areas or Greening Areas**

637 Another key aspect of a person's well-being is their income and livelihood. Research on
638 how income and livelihoods are affected by HEI presents mixed outcomes. Herrmann et al.
639 (2014) found better well-being in communities less focused on environmental quality, while
640 Castillo-Eguskiza et al. (2017) noted that protected areas boosted sustainability and local
641 quality of life. Dos Santos Facundes et al. (2024) warned that urban greening in vulnerable
642 areas might displace residents and worsen inequities. Thapa et al. (2024) added that land
643 ownership in megacities was positively linked to tree cover and urban greening.

644

645 **HEI Impact on Comprehensive Human Well-Being by Ecoregion (Environmental** 646 **Conditions), Industry-Dependence, State, and Ecosystem Quality**

647 Scown et al. (2017) assessed human well-being using an indicator that reflects the
648 availability of social, economic, and ecosystem services within a given area. In this study,
649 spatial multiple linear regression was used and, as a result, a total of 31% of the variance in
650 the county's human well-being was explained by ecoregion (environmental conditions),
651 industry-dependence, and state. Additionally, this study looked for relationships between
652 average human well-being indicators at the county level and watershed quality. Correlations
653 between county average human well-being and watershed quality were weak, and
654 Spearman's rank correlation coefficients ρ were less than 0.2.

655 Duku et al. (2022) observed that provisional ($\beta = 0.55$; $p \leq 0.001$) and cultural ($\beta = 0.374$;
656 $p \leq 0.05$) ecosystem services had a significant positive relationship with human well-being.
657 However, the relationship between regulating ecosystem services and human well-being was
658 significantly strong but reversed ($\beta = -0.87$; $p \leq 0.001$).

659 Analyzing the correlations of human well-being and ecosystem services (ES-HWB) in
660 China, Liu et al. (2022a) concluded that there were three types of clusters (regions): (1)
661 positive correlation, (2) negative correlation, and (3) no correlation. In addition, they found
662 that a positive ES-HWB relationship was found mainly in socio-economically
663 underdeveloped (rural or agricultural) regions with low ES production levels; a negative ES-
664 HWB relationship occurred mostly in intermediately developed regions with abundant non-
665 food ES; and ES and HWB had no relationships in socio-economically well-developed
666 (intensive agriculture/urbanized) societies with ample provisioning ES.

667 Zhang et al. (2024) concluded that economic, social, and technological factors positively
668 contributed to increasing well-being levels, while ecological effects, such as SO_2 pollution,
669 had a negative impact. Their analysis employed the entropy method, Dagum Gini coefficient,
670 and Logarithmic Mean Divisia Index (LMDI) decomposition to assess these influences.

671 Zhu et al. (2022) came up with an algorithm how to measure the efficiency with which
672 natural resources and the ecological environment were transformed into a corresponding level

673 of human well-being – economic growth, social equality (income of rural residents/income of
 674 urban residents), universal education health, favorable environment (green park space, air
 675 quality rate); they also concluded that for cities at different hierarchy levels, the effect of
 676 technological progress on the efficiency of well-being performance is different. High-level
 677 cities had a higher level of development and pursued green and high-quality development.

678

679 **Figure 14**

680 *Human Well-Being and Relations with Environmental and Socio-Economic Factors*

681 Note: Green lines represent relations between quantitative indicators. Human components are
 682 highlighted in orange, and environment components are highlighted in green.

683

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686 Figure 14 presents the interrelationships between quantitative indicators of human well-
 687 being and other indicators, such as environmental well-being, environmental factors, and
 688 socio-economic factors. It should be noted that causations are not indicated, because the
 689 examined articles often used correlation analyses or group comparisons rather than causal
 690 designs.

691 **Responses to Research Question 2**

692 *RQ2: What is the influence of the spatial dimension on well-being monitoring?*

693 The section presents results to highlight the role of spatial dimension in the reviewed
 694 literature. It is worth noting that this issue has been less addressed than that of the previous
 695 research question.

696 **Geographical Scale**

697 The majority of studies (46) were conducted at a regional scale, covering parts of one or
 698 more countries. Examples include research on forests (Aguilar et al., 2024; Bhatt et al.,
 699 2024), coastal areas (Bastos et al., 2023; Santos Vieira et al., 2021; Sajjad et al., 2019),

700 islands (Cordero-Penín et al., 2023; Newman et al., 2020), or mountain regions (Carilla et al.,
701 2024; Wang et al., 2023b) that cross several countries. Additionally, 16 studies focused on
702 the city scale or specific urban areas (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020a; Bonilla-Bedoya et al.,
703 2021; Dennis, & James, 2016; dos Santos Facundes et al., 2024; Kajosaari et al., 2024;
704 Klobuchar, et al. 2021; Li et al., 2025; Zeng et al., 2023), while four studies examined
705 national or global scales (Angelucci & Radogna, 2024; Mungi et al., 2023; Sietz et al., 2011;
706 Wang et al., 2023a). In several articles, the geographical scale was not explicitly defined. A
707 more detailed evaluation was performed on the 37 studies in which well-being indicators
708 were quantitatively measured (Table C.10; Table C.11). The overwhelming focus on regional
709 and city-scale research indicates a clear need for expanding well-being monitoring at the
710 local and community levels, where interventions and educational efforts are most effective.

711 **Temporal Scale**

712 Ten environmental and 17 human well-being observations were collected only at one
713 specific moment in time, as snapshots, rather than as continuous, long-term series of
714 observations. For example, for the habitat quality assessment, the risk of water pollution in
715 coastal industrialized areas is determined as a one-time measure, rather than a permanent
716 long-term measurement (Bastos et al., 2023). Another example is the study of the counts and
717 richness of Cultural Ecosystem services measured at a single point in time (Santos Vieira et
718 al., 2021). Svoray et al. (2018) study the geographic locations where people have happy
719 facial expressions in photographs, and this study also reflects a specific moment in time. Five
720 environmental and three human well-being measures are dynamical as they change over time.
721 For example, the study has assessed habitat quality and shown changes for the period from
722 2000 to 2020 (Wang et al., 2023a). In the study on the typhoon destructive potential for
723 coastal regions of China, the study period was from 1980 to 2014, which allowed observing
724 short-term geographical changes in typhoons (Sajjad et al., 2019). To study the spatial
725 representation of people's perceptions of changes in vegetation cover and NDVI trends, data
726 for the period from 1982 to 2008 were used (Herrmann et al., 2014). The heavy reliance on
727 "snapshot" studies, as opposed to dynamic, longitudinal ones, presents a major challenge for
728 understanding the complex feedback loops between human and environmental well-being
729 over time. This gap in the literature is a key area for future research and a significant
730 consideration for educators developing sustainability curricula.

731 **Monitoring Spatial Variations**

732 Results from 14 environmental and 15 human well-being studies are linked to geographic
733 location, showing differences between different areas. For example, Scown et al. (2017)
734 identified disparities (high and low levels) in the quality of surface watershed ecosystems and
735 human well-being at the county level (US). Bonilla-Bedoya et al. (2021) presented the spatial
736 variations in air pollution in the urban gradient of the Quito Metropolitan District. Sietz et al.
737 (2011) revealed the spatial distribution of the typical vulnerability patterns. A cluster analysis
738 revealed a set of seven typical vulnerability patterns showing combinations of distinct
739 indicators (poverty, water stress, soil degradation, natural agro-constraints, and isolation).
740 The study by Bonilla-Bedoya et al. (2020a) found the probable urbanization distribution in
741 the Metropolitan District of Quito. Bastos et al. (2023) noted spatial variations in risk across
742 the Ria de Aveiro's marine, coastal, estuarine, and freshwater habitats. Spatial variations have
743 also been discovered in studies on human well-being. For example, Beichler (2015) shows in
744 his study which geographic areas are the ones where people are most satisfied with the CES
745 supply. The research by Capecchi et al. (2021) shows the distribution of forest suitability for
746 stress level reduction. Bonilla-Bedoya et al. (2020a) observe the spatial variations of people's

747 perceived restoration and subjective well-being according to the origins of the respondents.
748 Zhu et al. (2022) examined the spatial distribution of ecological well-being performance in
749 China. Duku et al. (2022) published spatial variation maps of three human well-being levels
750 across Ghana's coastal areas. Liu et al. (2022a) found that the local-scale relationship
751 between ecosystem services and human well-being had spatial heterogeneity, varying from
752 positive to negative or no correlations across broad regions.

753 **Monitoring the Spatial Distribution of Impacting Factors**

754 Among the reviewed papers, ten environmental and four human well-being studies show
755 the spatial distribution of both well-being measurements and their influencing factors. Thus,
756 for example, in the study on habitat quality, the distribution of high-risk water pollution
757 stressors selected in the region of Aveiro is specified (Bastos et al., 2023). The study on
758 biodiversity monitoring indicates not only the distribution of the most vulnerable habitats, but
759 also the distribution of high-concern invasive plants at a national scale in India (Mungi et al.,
760 2023). In a study on human health and perceived restoration in nature, Bonilla-Bedoya et al.
761 (2020a) reflect the following distributions: land cover, density of green areas and urban
762 forests in the census blocks, local spatial dissimilarity, local spatial isolation, population
763 density, and socio-economic disparity (poor and non-poor). The study on air pollution
764 presents the spatial distribution of land cover influencing air quality (Bonilla-Bedoya et al.
765 2021). Kajosaari et al. (2024) present both probabilities of positive or negative perceptions of
766 urban green space quality and spatial distribution of availability of urban green space in
767 Espoo. Liu et al. (2022a) conclude that the variations and spatial patterns of the ecosystem
768 services and human well-being relationships are influenced by several social-ecological
769 factors, e.g., population density and land cover compositions.

770 **Discussion**

771 The section synthesizes the key insights emerged from the systematic review, highlighting
772 three primary themes: conceptual unclarity in defining well-being and human-environment
773 interactions, the challenge of establishing causal relationships, and the critical importance of
774 the spatial and temporal dimensions in well-being monitoring. The findings are relevant not
775 only for environmental science but also carry significant implications for teacher education
776 for sustainability, as educators play a central role in equipping future generations with the
777 knowledge, values, and critical thinking skills required to address sustainability challenges.

778 The review process prompted the interdisciplinary research team to confront the
779 prevalence of human-centered thinking in sustainability literature. While not all members
780 specialize in environmental studies, it has been collectively recognized how this dominant
781 perspective shapes education research. Discussions have revealed that even academic
782 frameworks positioning nature as “service-provider” inadvertently narrow sustainability
783 discourse. This realization now informs how the research team members, as education
784 researchers, approach sustainability – emphasizing its systemic nature beyond utilitarian
785 benefits. Through the systematic review, the research team has gained a deeper appreciation
786 for the conceptual inconsistencies and methodological gaps that currently characterize the
787 field. This experience underscores the research team's conviction that a more holistic and
788 integrated approach is essential to advancing both research and pedagogy.

789 **The Dominant “Anthropocentric” Approach and Personal Reflections on**
790 **Sustainability** The systematic review has examined articles addressing both human and
791 environmental well-being. The analysis confirms that the dominant framing is
792 anthropocentric – ecosystems and nature are often conceptualized primarily as resources or
793 service providers for human benefit (Bartelet et al., 2023; Beichler, 2016; Bonilla-Bedoya et

794 al., 2020a; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020b; Capecchi et al., 2021; Carone et al., 2017; Chai-
795 Allah et al., 2023; Cobacho et al., 2020). In contrast, holistic or ecocentric perspectives –
796 where humans are viewed as integral components of ecosystems – are rarely central to the
797 research design. While many articles recognize that environmental well-being is essential to
798 sustaining human well-being (Chen et al., 2023; de Guzman et al., 2022; Duku et al., 2022),
799 their primary focus often remains on improving human outcomes (Bastos et al., 2023;
800 Castillo-Eguskitz et al., 2017; Cordero-Penín et al., 2023). This reflects a persistent
801 anthropocentric bias, where environmental well-being is instrumentalized rather than valued
802 intrinsically.

803 This anthropocentric bias is a critical point for reflection in sustainability education, where
804 nature is frequently framed through a utilitarian lens. A more balanced, transdisciplinary
805 approach would emphasize ecosystem-centered pedagogy that promotes a deeper
806 understanding of interdependence, ecological ethics, and the intrinsic value of nature (Salite
807 et al., 2024). Such an approach has the potential to foster a robust biospheric consciousness
808 and align with research indicating that a shift in educational paradigms is needed to improve
809 environmental sustainability (Ferreira & Pitarma, 2021; Wals & Benavot 2017).

810 From a personal perspective, conducting this study has deepened the research team’s
811 understanding of sustainability beyond a simple definition of “meeting the needs of the
812 present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”
813 (United Nations, 2015). The research team has recognized sustainability not merely as a set
814 of policies or technological fixes, but as a profoundly ethical and relational concept. The
815 overwhelming anthropocentric bias in the literature reviewed has become, for the research
816 team, a powerful wake-up call. It has highlighted how deeply ingrained the idea of human
817 dominance is in the collective scientific and societal worldview. This research process has
818 become a journey of personal reflection, forcing the research team to confront personal
819 assumptions and biases about the human place in the natural world. True sustainability, as the
820 research team now understands, requires a paradigm shift – moving from a perspective in
821 which humanity manages nature for human benefit to one in which people see themselves as
822 an inseparable part of a complex, interconnected web of life. The authors acknowledge that
823 conducting this review has reinforced their commitment to embedding sustainability in
824 educational contexts. The authors believe that this shift must be cultivated through education,
825 equipping future generations with not only technical knowledge but also an ecocentric
826 worldview that values the intrinsic well-being of the planet. The process has not only
827 deepened the research team’s understanding of holistic sustainability perspectives but also
828 underscored the responsibility of educators and researchers to act as role models in aligning
829 educational practice with planetary well-being.

830 **Confusing Concepts and Definitions of Human and Environmental Well-Being and** 831 **Their Misleading Interactions**

832 A finding of this review is the lack of consensus around a single, coherent definition of
833 well-being across the literature. Well-being is interpreted through multiple frameworks.
834 Cambridge Dictionary (2022) defines well-being as “the state of feeling healthy and happy”.
835 The UK’s What Works Centre for Wellbeing emphasizes subjective dimensions such as life
836 satisfaction and emotional experience (Muller et al., 2021). According to the Organization for
837 Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (2020), well-being consists of three
838 domains: material conditions (e.g., income, housing), quality of life (e.g., health, education,
839 and environmental quality), and subjective well-being (e.g., life satisfaction). Most reviewed
840 articles align with this framework, focusing on subjective well-being, health, and economic

841 aspects. While the OECD definitions for human well-being are available, definitions for
842 environmental well-being could not be identified. In addition, it should be emphasized that
843 the term “environmental well-being” is used in only one article, while other articles use terms
844 referring to environmental quality or health. The authors contend that this terminological
845 preference underscores an anthropocentric approach, where the priority is placed on human
846 well-being and its direct relationship with the environment, rather than on the intrinsic value
847 of the environment itself. The systematic review has identified three aspects of environmental
848 well-being: (1) ecosystem health providing biodiversity and avoiding vulnerability (Bonilla-
849 Bedoya et al., 2020b; Dennis & James, 2016; Junker et al., 2015; Kajosaari et al., 2024;
850 Klobuchar et al. 2021; Santos Vieira et al., 2021; Scown et al., 2017; Sietz et al., 2011); (2)
851 habitat quality (Bastos et al., 2023; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2021; Mungi et al., 2023; Wang et
852 al., 2023a); (3) ecosystem resilience (Sajjad et al., 2019). Environmental well-being is also
853 related to sustainability (Angelstam et al., 2022; Castillo-Eguskita et al., 2017; de Alencar et
854 al., 2020; Gašparović et al., 2022; Klobucar et al., 2021; Newman et al., 2020). The United
855 Nations defines sustainability as “meeting the needs of the present without compromising the
856 ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (World Commission on Environment
857 and Development, 1987). To ensure the sustainability of living things, environmental well-
858 being must be congruent with sustained disease resistance, good nutrition, and the persistence
859 of species-appropriate population dynamics. However, considering the limited number of
860 systematic review articles, the authors of the present study believe that the concept of
861 environmental well-being needs to be further explored and discussed in the future.

862 Similarly, the concept of human-environment interaction is used inconsistently. Articles
863 portray humans as: (1) consumers of ecosystem services (Aguilar et al., 2024; Bhatt et al.,
864 2024; Cai et al., 2024; Duku et al., 2022; Ferguson et al., 2024; Liepa et al., 2023; Liu et al.,
865 2022b; Maass et al., 2005; Samuelsson et al., 2019); (2) modifiers of the environment (Bastos
866 et al., 2023; Beichler, 2015; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020a; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020b;
867 Carilla et al., 2024; de Guzman et al., 2022; Dennis & James, 2016; Kajosaari et al., 2024;
868 Liu et al., 2022a; Zeng et al., 2023; Zhu et al., 2022); (3) subjects affected by natural hazards
869 (Bartelet et al., 2023; Sajjad et al., 2019; Klobucar et al., 2021; Lamchin et al., 2022).

870 Two approaches dominate: first, research focuses on improving access to ecosystem
871 services (e.g., green spaces) (Beichler, 2015; de Guzman et al., 2022; Dennis & James, 2016;
872 Kajosaari et al., 2024; Klobucar et al., 2021; Molari et al., 2024; Zeng et al., 2023); second,
873 studies seek to identify which services most enhance well-being.

874 However, activities like urbanization (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020a; Liu et al., 2022a;
875 Thapa et al., 2024), industrialization (Bastos et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2022a), rural
876 development (Kohler et al., 2017), and forest management (Angelstam et al., 2022) often
877 prioritize economic benefits. These activities drive land-use changes that lead to the
878 degradation and reduced availability of essential ecosystem services.

879 Natural hazards affect humans’ lives in the following ways: increased air and water
880 temperatures lead to rising sea levels and higher wind speeds (Bartelet et al., 2023; Newman
881 et al., 2020; Sajjad et al., 2019). This reduces the ecosystem services available to humans.
882 People need to find solutions to adapt to the new conditions to maintain livelihood and
883 quality of life (Cobacho et al., 2020).

884 This lack of conceptual clarity can mislead both scientific interpretation and educational
885 practice. Clear, context-sensitive definitions are essential, particularly in sustainability-
886 oriented teacher education, where students must be able to navigate the complexity and
887 ambiguity inherent in environmental discourse (McFarlane & Ogazon, 2011; Ram et al.,

888 2025).

889 **Uncertainty in Quantitative Relationships Between Human/Environmental Well-Being** 890 **and Influencing Factors**

891 Many studies rely on statistical associations rather than methods that reveal causality,
892 limiting an understanding of what truly influences well-being. Additionally, in some studies,
893 the quantitative relationships revealed for well-being-related variables are weak or non-
894 existent. For instance, Scown et al. (2017) reported very weak correlations ($\rho < 0.2$) between
895 watershed quality and human well-being indicators. Similarly, Chen et al. (2023) found
896 statistically significant but weak correlations, e.g., between bird species richness and life
897 expectancy ($r = 0.18$; $p < 0.001$). These examples illustrate that correlation alone may not
898 capture the complex dynamics of human-environment relationships. Human-environment
899 relationships are complex and not very often subject to linearity. Therefore, it is necessary to
900 look for other more effective ways to determine the relationships, including causal
901 relationships. The use of correlations has weaknesses and limitations. The obtained
902 correlations do not indicate a causal relationship; the authors of the articles themselves point
903 out this deficiency (Angermeier et al., 2021).

904 Moreover, findings across studies are often contradictory. Some report that CES and green
905 areas impact subjective well-being (Beichler, 2015; Molari et al., 2024; Svoray et al., 2018;
906 Wang et al., 2023b; Zeng et al., 2023); while others find no significant effect, for example, no
907 relationship between urban green areas or forests and subjective well-being has been
908 discovered (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020a).

909 Studies also diverge on whether improving environmental conditions leads to improved
910 human well-being. For example, Herrmann et al. (2014) have concluded that the livelihood
911 and well-being variables evolve more positively in communities that do not care about the
912 quality of the environment (non-greening communities). Also, Duku et al. (2022) have
913 concluded that human well-being and regulatory ecosystem services are inversely correlated,
914 the higher human well-being is rated, the lower the indicators for such ecosystem services
915 that control the level of air, land, and water pollution. On the other hand, Castillo-Eguskitza
916 et al. (2017) state that the protected area fulfills its sustainability goal and enhances the local
917 population's quality of life. The fact that there is no clear connection between human and
918 environmental well-being is also evidenced by other articles excluded from the systematic
919 review.

920 Larger-scale analyses reinforce this ambiguity. Van de Kerk and Manuel (2012) observed
921 an average negative correlation between Human Well-being (HW) and Environmental Well-
922 being (EW) across 151 countries. Also, Ulman et al. (2020) analyzed the effects of human
923 well-being on environmental well-being and concluded that a high level of HW has a
924 negative influence on the level of EW (path coef = -0.585 , Sig = 0.000), indicating a tendency
925 to decrease its level. However, Ulman et al. (2020) conducted a separate analysis of countries
926 with factor-driven economies and innovation-driven economies and concluded that the
927 influence of HW on EW is negative in factor-driven economies with path coef = -0.787 and
928 Sig = 0.000 and positive in innovation-driven economies with path coef = 0.588 and Sig
929 = 0.003 .

930 Given that human-environment interactions form a complex and dynamic system, the
931 authors of the present study conclude that the dominant use of statistical methods is
932 inadequate for fully capturing these linkages. While some articles have begun to apply AI and
933 machine learning techniques (Li et al., 2025; Liu et al., 2024; Santos Vieira et al., 2021; Vigil
934 et al., 2021), their use is not widespread. Therefore, the authors of the present study assert

935 that future research must prioritize advanced methodologies, including dynamic modeling
 936 and machine learning, to better quantify and, most importantly, identify causalities between
 937 human and environmental well-being. Notably, the systematic review emphasizes the critical
 938 absence of a feedback loop from human well-being to environmental well-being in the
 939 existing literature – an essential mechanism for ensuring long-term environmental
 940 sustainability. Figure 15 provides a conceptual perspective, illustrating the current situation
 941 and the desired future state, highlighting where quantitative causation studies are most
 942 needed to complete this feedback loop.

943

944 **Figure 15**

945 *A Conceptual Perspective on Human-Environment Interactions and the Causal Relationships*
 946 *of Well-Being*

947 Note: Black lines are conclusions about theoretical links from the reviewed literature, red
 948 lines are the ones where quantitative causation studies are needed. Human components are
 949 highlighted in orange, and environment components are highlighted in green.

950

951

952 (a) Current situation

(b) Desired future situation

953 Embedding systems thinking and basic modeling into sustainability education can help
 954 students understand these interdependencies and develop skills to work with complexity
 955 (Dias et al., 2022; Iliško et al., 2017; Salīte et al., 2024). A major gap identified is the limited
 956 number of studies that establish quantitative or causal links between human or environmental
 957 well-being and influencing factors. While statistical analysis is common, few studies explore
 958 dynamic or feedback-driven models. This presents a challenge and an opportunity for
 959 education. Embedding these approaches in training helps future educators critically assess the
 960 interconnected nature of ecological, social, and economic systems. As Zandvliet and Paul
 961 (2023) argue, ecological problems cannot be fully understood or solved without
 962 acknowledging the irrationalities and complexities within our current societal systems.

963 **Spatial Dimension of Well-Being Monitoring**

964 The present analysis underscores the essential, often underexplored, role of the spatial and
 965 temporal dimensions in well-being monitoring. The spatial dimension allows for targeted,
 966 place-based interventions, which are crucial for enhancing quality of life and addressing
 967 disparities. Monitoring well-being means regularly collecting, analyzing, and using data to
 968 manage human-environment interactions, enhance positive outcomes, and reduce risks
 969 (BetterEvaluation, 2022).

970 Spatial variations affect access to essential services and resources (Beichler, 2015; dos
971 Santos Facundes et al., 2024; Duku et al., 2022; Zhu et al. 2022). Well-being monitoring in
972 different locations helps identify disparities in access to healthcare, education, employment
973 opportunities, social services, and ecosystem services (Bonilla-Bedoya et al. 2020a; Capecchi
974 et al., 2021; Duku et al., 2022). This information guides the allocation of resources to address
975 these disparities, ultimately enhancing well-being (Liu et al., 2022b; Santos Vieira et al.,
976 2021). Spatial analysis considers the quality of the environment within different geographical
977 areas (Bastos et al., 2023; Mungi et al., 2023; Scown et al., 2017). Monitoring environmental
978 factors, such as air quality (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2021) and water quality (Sietz et al., 2011),
979 green spaces (dos Santos Facundes et al., 2024; Kajosaari et al., 2024; Thapa et al., 2024),
980 land cover (Herrmann et al., 2014), and exposure to pollution, helps in understanding how the
981 environment impacts residents' well-being. Spatial dimensions aid in identifying and
982 addressing disparities to improve overall well-being. This spatial lens is also essential for
983 effective policymaking (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020b; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2021; Duku et
984 al., 2022; Sajjad et al., 2019; Svoray et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2023b; Zhu et al., 2022) and
985 for education. In sustainability education, spatial awareness enables learners to connect
986 abstract concepts to real-life challenges, as engaging students in localized, field-based
987 activities and spatial tasks enhances their environmental literacy and connection to place
988 (Saraiva et al., 2024).

989 **Scales of Monitoring**

990 The systematic review has revealed a significant imbalance in the scale of monitoring. A
991 limited number of researchers focus on conducting studies at the local level (Bonilla-Bedoya
992 et al., 2020b; Dennis, & James, 2016; dos Santos Facundes et al., 2024; Kajosaari et al.,
993 2024; Klobuchar, et al. 2021). Most research projects are conducted at the regional level, not
994 measured for small territories (local scale) (Angermeier et al., 2021; Bastos et al., 2023;
995 Beichler, 2015; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020a; Capecchi et al., 2021; Castillo-Eguskitza et al.,
996 2017; Chen et al., 2023; Duku et al., 2022; Herrmann et al., 2014; Sajjad et al., 2019; Santos
997 Vieira et al., 2021; Svoray et al., 2018; Thapa et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023b; Zhang et al.,
998 2024). While monitoring well-being at various scales is important for a comprehensive
999 understanding, the local scale is particularly significant due to its contextual relevance, ability
1000 to identify community-specific needs, and the potential for tailored, impactful interventions
1001 that directly improve the well-being of the community (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020b; Dennis,
1002 & James, 2016; Fry et al., 2017; Kajosaari et al., 2024). The choice of monitoring scale
1003 should align with research goals and available resources.

1004 Similarly, a temporal gap exists, with few studies tracking well-being over time (Bonilla-
1005 Bedoya et al., 2021; Castillo-Eguskitza et al., 2017; Herrmann et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2024;
1006 Sajjad et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2023a; Yi et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024), limiting the
1007 potential for tracking change or causality. Most data are collected at a single time point,
1008 which constrains an understanding of dynamic trends (Angermeier et al., 2021; Bastos et al.,
1009 2023; Beichler, 2015; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020b; Cai et al., 2024; Dennis & James, 2016;
1010 Duku et al., 2022; Kajosaari et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2022b; Mungi et al., 2023; Santos Vieira
1011 et al., 2021; Scown et al., 2017; Svoray et al., 2018; Thapa et al., 2024; Zhu et al., 2022).

1012 From a sustainability education perspective, fostering understanding of both spatial and
1013 temporal dimensions helps students and future educators recognize the layered and evolving
1014 nature of environmental and social issues. Embedding these elements in teacher education
1015 encourages place-based learning and systems thinking (Abdallah, 2025; Zandvliet & Paul,
1016 2023; Wanchana et al., 2020). Localized data is crucial to understanding disparities and

1017 enabling community-level interventions. This supports the integration of place-based
1018 education and geospatial thinking into sustainability pedagogy. Educators can use such
1019 approaches to connect abstract sustainability goals with learners' everyday environments,
1020 fostering stronger place identity and stewardship.

1021 Traditionally, data is captured through surveys of householders (Wang et al., 2023a; Duku
1022 et al., 2022; Junker et al., 2015), forest attendees (Capecchi et al., 2021; Liepa et al., 2023),
1023 residential property owners (Klobuchar et al., 2021), and field experts (Bastos et al., 2023;
1024 Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020a). There is an issue of incomplete country coverage, incomplete
1025 time series, and untimely data (Junker et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2023b). Surveys can be time-
1026 consuming, expensive, and labor-intensive (Tingzon et al., 2019). Therefore, it is necessary to
1027 look for data sources where there are no problems with access and use, and the data is
1028 regularly updated.

1029 Satellite data has significant but underused potential for assessing well-being at local
1030 scales (Jean et al., 2016; Yeh et al., 2020). It can reflect land-use intensity and agricultural
1031 trends not visible in survey data (Burke & Lobell, 2017; Kubitz et al., 2020; Lobell et al.,
1032 2020; Nguyen et al., 2020; Viana et al., 2019).

1033 **The Potential of Satellite Data**

1034 Despite these benefits, few reviewed studies utilize satellite or remote sensing data
1035 (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020a; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2020b; Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2021; dos
1036 Santos Facundes et al., 2024; Herrmann et al., 2014; Li et al., 2025; Mungi et al., 2023;
1037 Sajjad et al., 2019; Thapa et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023a), and some highlight issues, such as
1038 weak correlation between satellite-observed and perceived environmental changes (Herrmann
1039 et al., 2014). Hargreaves & Watmough (2020) argue that satellite-based monitoring of well-
1040 being is still emerging and requires new methodologies. Bonilla-Bedoya et al. (2020a) also
1041 stress the need for fine-scale, socio-ecologically informed spatial-temporal indicators. These
1042 findings indicate an opportunity to expand satellite data integration both in research and
1043 education. In educational contexts, however, satellite data use remains limited due to
1044 technical, motivational, and informational barriers (Asimakopoulou et al., 2023).
1045 Sustainability education would benefit from incorporating remote sensing into curricula,
1046 improving students' digital literacy and analytical skills (Danaher et al., 2021).

1047 **Limitations of the Systematic Review**

1048 The systematic review has several limitations that should be considered. First, the findings
1049 have been constrained by the scope of the search strategy, which has focused on a specific set
1050 of keywords and databases. While comprehensive, this approach may have inadvertently
1051 omitted relevant literature from related disciplines, such as sociology, public health, or
1052 economics, that also addresses human-environment interactions. The review is limited to
1053 studies published in indexed academic databases, potentially excluding relevant grey
1054 literature and non-English sources. Second, as a qualitative synthesis of existing literature,
1055 this review does not allow for a quantitative meta-analysis of results. Methodological
1056 diversity among the included studies has posed challenges for direct comparison. The authors
1057 of the present study, therefore, rely on a narrative approach to highlight trends and
1058 inconsistencies. Third, the synthesis has been influenced by the interdisciplinary backgrounds
1059 of the authors, which, while enriching interpretation, may also introduce subjective bias.
1060 Finally, the limitations identified within the reviewed articles themselves – such as the
1061 prevalent reliance on correlational data, single time-point analyses, and a dominant regional
1062 scale – are inherent limitations of the findings. The research conclusions are a direct
1063 reflection of the current state of the field, highlighting persistent gaps that require further

1064 empirical and methodological exploration to advance the understanding of well-being in the
1065 context of human-environment dynamics.

1066 **Conclusions and Implications for Sustainability Education**

1067 The systematic review has examined human-environment well-being monitoring and
1068 identified factors influencing well-being, as well as the data sources and methods used to
1069 characterize well-being processes. The focus of the well-being research has been from the
1070 perspective of interaction between people and the environment. The study has addressed two
1071 research questions: How do human-environment interactions are connected to well-being?
1072 What is the influence of the spatial dimension on well-being monitoring? Using the
1073 predefined keywords, the study has identified 73 relevant articles for the systematic review.

1074 Based on the analysis, it is possible to draw the main conclusions provided below. (1) The
1075 dominant approach across studies is anthropocentric – ecosystems and nature are mainly
1076 viewed as tools or services for human benefit. Holistic or ecocentric frameworks, where
1077 humans are embedded within ecosystems, are rarely the primary research focus. (2) There is a
1078 lack of research that establishes quantitative or causal links between well-being and its
1079 influencing factors. While statistical methods are common, there is notable potential to apply
1080 dynamic models and explore empirical causation. Notably, links between human-
1081 environment interactions and their impact on both human and environmental well-being
1082 remain underexplored. 3) Most studies focus on national or regional scales, with limited
1083 attention to small-scale (local) well-being monitoring. 4) The articles lack perspective on the
1084 local scale, dynamical models, and satellite data usage.

1085 The review has also identified key challenges and gaps in the current research on human
1086 and environmental well-being interactions. These findings are valuable for researchers,
1087 policymakers, and educators aiming to improve sustainability outcomes.

1088 Based on the gaps identified, the authors of the present study recommend the following
1089 future areas for research and practice: (1) Expand local-scale research using geolocalized
1090 well-being factors; (2) Explore approaches related to dynamic data modelling and causal
1091 analysis; (3) Identify new approaches based on technologies for well-being data collection
1092 and analysis such as satellite imaging analysis; 4) Develop methods to establish a feedback
1093 loop between human well-being and environmental well-being; (5) Assess the limitations of
1094 well-being models in socio-ecological system context; (6) Identify the challenges of well-
1095 being research extension towards well-being models upgrade with data from different online
1096 information systems.

1097 The research findings present clear implications for teacher education for sustainability.
1098 The authors of the present study advocate for integrating dynamic modeling and satellite data
1099 analysis into teacher training, equipping educators to address sustainability challenges with
1100 both technical and ethical competence. While these methods show theoretical promise based
1101 on the review findings, their implementation would require careful adaptation to different
1102 educational contexts. The challenge is to train future educators to transcend the dominant
1103 anthropocentric view by incorporating ecocentric pedagogies and a systems-thinking
1104 approach. This involves teaching them to critically analyze the conceptual inconsistencies
1105 they will encounter in academic literature and media, and to understand that a truly
1106 sustainable future requires valuing the environment intrinsically. Furthermore, to prepare
1107 students for the complexities of real-world environmental challenges, educators must be
1108 equipped with the skills to integrate local, place-based learning with dynamic, data-driven
1109 analysis. This includes the effective use of emerging technologies like satellite data and
1110 dynamic models to move from a static understanding of problems to a dynamic and

1111 predictive one. Ultimately, this will empower a new generation of learners to not only
1112 understand sustainability but to actively and effectively contribute to it. Future studies should
1113 prioritise longitudinal, participatory action research involving teacher educators and learners
1114 in co-creating sustainability curricula. Expanding research to underrepresented cultural
1115 contexts and incorporating non-English scholarship could enhance inclusivity. The research
1116 findings underscore the urgency of reforming teacher education to include ecocentric
1117 frameworks, systems thinking, and geospatial technologies, fostering a generation of
1118 educators who can navigate the complexities of sustainability.

1119

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1126

1127 **Data Availability.** The data generated and analyzed during the current
1128 study (including the appendices referenced in the paper) are publicly
1129 available at: <https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/5brjhxr8nx/2>

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